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***HRJust WP 4 Report
the Rights of the Child during the COVID-19 Pandemic
vulnerability, intersectionality, and human rights
justifications:
A Civil Society Perspective***

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HRJust WP 4 Report: the Rights of the Child during the COVID-19 Pandemic vulnerability, intersectionality, and human rights justifications: A Civil Society Perspective

Executive Summary

This report examines the human rights and children's rights implications of the COVID-19 responses in Sweden and Finland, focusing on the balance between conflicting constitutional and human rights and the national structures for civil society engagement during emergencies like the pandemic. Both countries faced the challenge of protecting public health during the pandemic; however, children, while not the most at risk of suffering from the virus itself, were significantly affected by the restrictions.

The purpose and scope of this report is twofold. First, it explores the views of human rights advocates regarding COVID-19 restrictions, particularly those imposed on educational institutions, such as the transition to distance learning, and assesses whether these measures had discriminatory effects on specific groups of children, including those from minority backgrounds. Second, it examines the role of civil society in decision-making during the pandemic. Both Sweden and Finland have a notable history of engaging civil society actors in policymaking, a relationship that has generally benefited all parties involved. However, it appears that some of these well-established structures for civil society engagement were undermined during the crisis.

Findings indicate that both Finnish and Swedish civil society actors faced challenges due to a lack of transparency in decision-making during the pandemic. In Finland, rapid legislative changes occurred without adequate public consultation, while Sweden's reliance on existing legal frameworks limited opportunities for NGOs to voice their concerns. Most interviewees expressed understanding of the urgency faced by governments but noted that this led to inadequate engagement and reliance on information produced by state organs, which limited the possibilities for proactive human rights and children's rights advocacy.

The paper also discusses the shortcomings of human rights impact assessments conducted by both governments. Interviewees noted that Finland's focus on fundamental rights often overlooked international human rights perspectives, while Sweden's minimal legislative changes resulted in insufficient documentation for assessing human rights implications. Furthermore, child impact assessments in the drafting phase were found to be lacking, with a tendency to ignore indirect and long-term impacts. Although the interviewees generally aligned with the restriction measures their respective governments resorted to, they noted that these measures led to structural discrimination against socio-economically disadvantaged children, who suffered disproportionately during the pandemic. The transition to remote learning in Finland raised concerns about the negative impact on children from immigrant backgrounds, who faced challenges related to language and access to information and support.

In conclusion, while some interviewees criticized their governments' responses, most attributed the lack of civil society engagement to the urgency of the situation. The interviewees called for the integration of human rights and children's rights perspectives into emergency planning and decision-making processes to ensure that the needs of vulnerable groups are adequately addressed, even in times of crisis. They also advocated for stronger institutional safeguards to protect human rights and the rights of the child during crises when broad civil society engagement is not possible.

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1 Introduction

This report examines the human rights and children's rights implications of the COVID-19 responses in Sweden and Finland, focusing on the balance between conflicting constitutional and human rights and the national structures for civil society engagement during emergencies like the pandemic. Throughout the COVID-19 pandemic, both Finland and Sweden faced the challenge of protecting public health and well-being. In retrospect, children are widely viewed as a group that suffered significant harm due to the restrictions, despite not being the demographic most at risk. Whether the cure was in that regard, worse than the disease, is a constant subject of debate, with Finland and Sweden offering two very different perspectives on the matter.

The purpose and scope of this report is twofold. First, it explores the views of the human rights advocates related to COVID-19 restrictions, particularly those imposed on educational institutions, such as the transition to distance learning, and assesses whether these measures had discriminatory effects on specific groups of children, including those from minority backgrounds. Second, it examines the role of civil society in decision-making during the pandemic. Both Sweden and Finland have a notable history of engaging civil society actors in policymaking, a relationship that has generally benefited all parties involved. However, it appears that some of these well-established structures for civil society engagement were undermined during the crisis.

This paper builds on the first deliverable of the Work Package No. 4 on Covid-19 Human Rights Justifications in Government Responses to COVID-19 in Sweden, Finland and Taiwan, as well as the relevant literature on the impacts of COVID-19 on children and young people. The primary contribution of this paper lies in its empirical approach; the issues are examined through the lens of civil society actors. By focusing on the perspectives of experts operating in both Sweden and Finland, two neighboring states that weighed and balanced human very rights differently, resulting in distinct COVID-19 response, this paper facilitates a brief and practical comparative analysis of societal structures and what could be done to improve them to accommodate debate on human rights even during a crisis.

2 Methodology

The primary research material consists of interviews conducted to gather insights from individuals working for non-governmental organizations (NGOs) focused on children's rights as well as human rights in general. The Five interviewees, two (2) from Sweden and three (3) from Finland were selected based on their positions within civil society organizations dedicated to fundamental rights, human rights, and children's rights, as well as their personal expertise:

Lena K., a legal expert in a well-established Swedish children's rights NGO.

Johanna A., an expert specialized in COVID-issues in Sweden

Sara L., a senior human rights specialist in a Finnish NGO promoting human rights

Paula O., a senior human rights expert in a Finnish human rights NGO

Susan H., an expert in a well-established Finnish child welfare organization.

In the semi-structured interviews conducted in April 2026, participants were asked to reflect on the COVID-19 restrictions imposed on children and youth in their respective countries,

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assessing their proportionality and implications for children's rights and human rights. Particular attention was given to restrictions related to educational institutions and the transition to remote learning as a specific countermeasure against COVID-19. The interviews were recorded and transcribed to enable proper analysis. Following the initial interviews, participants are granted the opportunity to comment on preliminary research results to encourage discussion among different perspectives regarding the impacts of COVID-19 restrictions. The findings are reported pseudonymized.

It should be noted that the methodological choices and scope of this paper inevitably lead to information being produced from a particular perspective: the aim is not to generate quantitative data but to enrich the existing body of research on the human rights implications of COVID-19 measures, particularly those concerning children, by focusing on the lived experiences and expertise of civil society actors.

3 Findings

3.1 Civil Society Engagement

Interviewees from both Sweden and Finland expressed that conditions for human rights and children's rights advocacy were hindered by a lack of transparency in decision-making during the early stages of the pandemic. In Finland, new legislation was introduced rapidly without broad public consultation. Although the government has internal guidelines for hearing processes during law-making, these were often not adhered to when drafting COVID-19 countermeasures. Susan H., an expert from a well-established Finnish child welfare organization, described decision-making as partially transparent but constrained by urgency and uncertainty, particularly during the early stages of the pandemic. While information about measures was made public, the rapid pace of decision-making and the evolving knowledge base limited opportunities for in-depth scrutiny and advocacy. This view was typical among the Finnish interviewees, all of whom reported that their organizations generally did not receive formal consultation requests concerning pandemic-specific restrictive measures and when consultations did occur, they usually concerned isolated issues rather than systemic engagement.

In contrast, Sweden's reliance on its pre-existing legal framework, without significant legislative changes, resulted in few opportunities for NGOs to be formally heard. Consequently, similarly to Finland, NGOs in Sweden learned of the latest developments in the government's response to the virus simultaneously with the general public, limiting their ability to engage in proactive advocacy through informal channels. This lack of transparency was present at the national, regional, and local levels, especially during the early stages of the pandemic. Johanna A., an expert specialized in COVID-19 issues in Sweden, recalled that debates over COVID-19 policies were highly polarized, with government authorities strongly supporting the distinctly different Swedish approach, which deliberately deviated from European Union norms and dismissing dissenting voices calling for stronger health protections. In her account, this polarization contributed to a challenging environment for meaningful children's rights advocacy. Finnish interviewees did not report similar polarization in the debate climate but instead highlighted ambiguity in decision-making.

Outside formal consultation processes, Susan H.'s experience was the most positive among the Finnish interviewees. She noted that her organization's recognized and longstanding role in Finnish society may have made it easier to maintain access to policymakers throughout the crisis. She felt that decision-makers remained willing to engage with the organization despite the exceptional circumstances. Finnish interviewees also reported that conditions for non-COVID-related human and children's rights advocacy were broadly similar to those in non-crisis situations, with varying degrees of civil society engagement, though their experiences were primarily positive. Similarly, Lena K., a legal expert at a well-established Swedish children's rights NGO, explained that despite the absence of formal legislative consultation during the pandemic, established informal advocacy channels allowed NGOs like hers to engage with the government and raise concerns effectively. According to her, as the pandemic progressed, debate and decision-making became more open, and NGOs were again more actively engaged in policymaking.

All interviewees acknowledged the urgent need to develop a COVID-19 response to protect the rights to health and life, despite the lack of adequate research data at the time. Many interviewees indicated that, particularly at the beginning of the pandemic, their organizations were ill-equipped and insufficiently informed to engage meaningfully in discussions about the human rights implications of COVID-19 measures. As a result, they focused instead on information gathering and resilience-building, implementing pre-planned human rights initiatives, or supporting affected communities locally during the crisis.

Finnish interviewees Sara L., Susan H., and Paula O., a human rights expert from a Finnish NGO, expressed trust in Finnish institutions and the rule of law. They noted that, especially in the early phase of the pandemic, their organizations relied on the expertise of public authorities and recognized their own limited capacity to independently scrutinize complex epidemiological and legal assessments. Consequently, they reported that they were not initially overly concerned about the human rights implications of restrictive measures or the lack of formal consultation.

Swedish interviewees appeared somewhat more critical of state actors than their Finnish counterparts. For example, Johanna A. criticized the government's approach, noting that it was more inclined to listen to NGOs that did not challenge its COVID-19 strategy, while critical voices advocating for more robust protective measures went largely unheard. Another Swedish interviewee, Lena K., emphasized that the government had to act quickly because it did not respond to the spread of COVID-19 in Europe in January 2020. By late February and early March, when official responses were formulated, the virus had already spread within Sweden, necessitating rapid action. While she understood the lack of civil society engagement in that specific context, she noted that this situation might have been avoidable.

3.2 Child Impact Assessments and the Best Interest of the Child

Sweden ratified the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child in 1990 but formally incorporated the CRC into its legal system on January 1, 2020, whereas Finland ratified the Convention in 1991. Lena K. described how the process of integrating the CRC into domestic legislation involved active collaboration among state authorities, municipalities, regional administrations, and civil society actors shortly before the pandemic. While this recent focus on

children's rights contributed to stronger protection compared to the broader human rights regime, the emergency mode adopted by Swedish society nonetheless resulted in setbacks for children's rights advocacy. Despite these positive developments, the institutional structures for implementing CRC requirements and integrating children's rights perspectives into ordinary law-making processes were still under development. Consequently, there was a significant lack of expertise regarding how the new legal framework should be applied to safeguard children's rights during emergencies such as the pandemic. Moreover, the urgency of introducing COVID-19 countermeasures meant that interventions by children's rights advocates often failed to receive adequate attention.

Lena K. further noted that even in the absence of formal civil society consultation processes, children's perspectives were incorporated into decisions or, in some cases, non-decisions, affecting children, arguably more so than in many other Western countries. She attributed this to Sweden's exceptional (non-)decision to keep preschools and primary schools open, while allowing pupils in grades 7–9 to shift to distance learning under specific local circumstances. She acknowledged that although the decision to keep primary education institutions open was beneficial, many other measures unnecessarily infringed upon children's rights. According to her, particularly problematic decisions lacked prior child rights impact assessments, although local authorities sometimes conducted post hoc analyses. In general, Sweden lacks standardized guidelines for conducting pre-emptive child rights impact assessments.

Johanna A. offered a markedly different perspective, describing decision-making processes affecting children as profoundly lacking in transparency. This opacity extended to fundamental and human rights impact assessments, including child impact assessments, which, where they existed at all, were limited in scope, inaccessible, or based on inaccurate assumptions about children's susceptibility to illness. These assumptions effectively excluded physical health considerations from assessment frameworks. Johanna A. observed that both officials and many children's rights advocates largely confined their attention to mental health impacts, while deliberately avoiding medical aspects of the pandemic.

In the Finnish context, Susan H. emphasized the role of NGOs in information gathering and dissemination during the pandemic, particularly in light of limited available data and the comparatively slow initial response of public authorities. She argued that NGOs were at times better positioned than officials to gather grassroots-level information on how COVID-19 was affecting children and young people, which could then be communicated to decision-makers. This information was reportedly well received by policymakers and public officials, who subsequently initiated cooperative exchanges with the organization. Nevertheless, Susan H. noted that such engagement did not always translate into outcomes that adequately balanced children's rights with broader human rights considerations, and results often fell short of organizational expectations. She further observed that even under normal circumstances, child impact assessments tend to be insufficient, frequently emphasizing positive aspects while neglecting indirect, negative, and long-term effects. The pandemic, she noted, was no exception. However, Susan H. did not recall any reluctance on the part of legislators to acknowledge critical or cautionary input from civil society regarding the implications of COVID-19 measures for children's rights, despite their failure to assess these impacts proactively ex officio.

Interviewees from both countries highlighted the importance of embedding children’s rights perspectives systematically into law-making processes, ensuring that the obligation to respect these rights is upheld even in crisis situations and even without external prompting. Lena K. and Susan H. in particular emphasized the need for a pre-planned, evidence-based emergency response strategy that explicitly incorporates and prioritizes children’s rights, along with a clear understanding of the legal and institutional safeguards required to protect those rights. Central to this approach is the systematic conduct of child rights impact assessments to ensure that crisis-related decisions are informed by children’s needs and rights. Reflecting on the pandemic, Susan H. underscored the importance of learning from previous shortcomings and identifying groups whose experiences remained insufficiently visible. A similar approach was reflected in many other interviews.

3.3. School closures and conflicting rights

Sweden and Finland adopted markedly different approaches when deciding whether educational institutions should remain open or be closed during the most acute stages of the pandemic. Finland declared a state of emergency in March 2020 and closed all primary, secondary, and tertiary educational institutions, as well as daycare centers, with the exception of limited childcare provision for essential workers. Sweden, by contrast, kept preschools and schools for children aged 7–15 open. Upper secondary schools were temporarily moved to distance learning during periods in 2020, and localized closures could be ordered under specific conditions.

Finland

In the Finnish context, Sara L., Susan H., and Paula O. described how preventing the transmission of COVID-19 became the overriding priority, creating a hierarchy of values that none of the represented organizations contested during the acute phase of the crisis. Restrictions affecting children such as prolonged periods of distance education and limitations on social interaction, were largely accepted at the time, particularly when framed as necessary to protect older persons and other risk groups. Susan H. noted that her organization lacked the capacity and expertise and relevant data at the time to challenge restrictive measures such as school closures. As the pandemic progressed, her organization emphasized children’s vulnerability and advocated for national-level guidance on mitigating measures, such as ensuring access to school meals during distance learning. These efforts sought to address the unequal effects of school closures, which disproportionately affected socioeconomically disadvantaged households and children from migrant backgrounds and

With hindsight, however, Sara L., Paula O., and Susan H. all assessed the shift to distance education as disproportionately severe, with profound consequences for children and young people. Although school closures and remote education were relatively short-lived restrictive measures, they nonetheless constituted drastic interventions. These retrospective evaluations are shaped by current knowledge that COVID-19 posed comparatively low medical risks to children, making such assessments more straightforward than at the time, when concerns about transmission from schools to households were widely regarded as legitimate. Susan. H asserts that the disproportionality of the school closures was further fueled by the lack of knowledge of remedies available to children. Data gathered from the time indicates that many children who

would likely have been entitled to special educational support due to a disability or learning difficulties and consequently often to in-person instruction even in the period of remote learning, were not even aware of this entitlement. If a family additionally faced for example language barriers or other difficulties in accessing information or if no one actively provides such information, it is unlikely that the family would have been able to exercise these remedies.

Sweden

As noted above, Lena K. considers children's perspectives to have been strongly reflected in Sweden's exceptional (non-)decision to keep preschools and primary schools open, while allowing pupils in grades 7–9 to shift to distance learning only under particular local circumstances. Although there are no *travaux préparatoires* outlining the rationale for not closing preschools and primary schools, given that this was not a formal decision, this approach was grounded in the best interests of the child, particularly for children in vulnerable situations. Continued access to schooling was viewed as critical, alongside the epidemiological understanding at the time that children were less likely than adults to contract and transmit the virus. Lena K. does not, however, consider NGO advocacy during the pandemic to have played a decisive role in the decision to keep schools open, as opportunities for such advocacy were limited. Rather, she suggests that the decision was partly the result of long-standing civil society efforts to incorporate the CRC into Swedish law and policy, emphasizing the principle of the child's best interests and the importance of maintaining children's access to education even in emergency situations, an approach previously reflected, for example, in foreign aid contexts.

Johanna A., by contrast, takes the opposite view, arguing that schools played a central role in the early spread of the virus in Sweden, affecting both students and teachers. She contends that the decision not to close schools for younger children, combined with a failure to implement compensatory risk-reduction measures such as mask mandates, preventive testing, improved ventilation, and later vaccination for younger age groups amounted to a systematic denial of children's right to health and, ultimately, their right to life.

Regarding upper secondary and vocational schools, Lena K. asserts that decisions to move these institutions to distance learning were largely unchallenged by both the public and NGOs. In hindsight, she believes that more robust child rights analyses should have preceded these decisions, together with efforts to mitigate their consequences, for instance through hybrid teaching models. Johanna A., on the other hand, questioned whether improved risk-mitigation measures in schools could have allowed secondary educational institutions to remain open for longer periods, thereby reducing the harmful impacts experienced by adolescents during the pandemic.

3.4 Human rights justifications and balancing of rights

Despite differences in legal frameworks and crisis responses between Finland and Sweden, when asked to evaluate whether their respective governments conducted adequate human and fundamental rights impact assessments during the COVID-19 pandemic, all interviewees identified significant shortcomings. In both countries, the assessments were widely perceived to be insufficiently attentive to human rights and children's rights, particularly in relation to

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vulnerable groups.

Finland

Finland adopted what hybrid strategy, combining soft-law recommendations and hard-law measures, including the use of emergency powers during the states of emergency declared in spring 2020 and spring 2021. Paula O. explains that at the time, her organization worked on specific issues relating to the right to health and attempted to integrate pandemic-related considerations into general legislative consultations whenever possible. The organization also engaged in proactive advocacy, highlighting human rights problems arising from lockdowns. She describes the Finnish government's early pandemic response as cautious, initially relying on voluntary measures and recommendations before gradually tightening restrictions. This approach was generally regarded as justified, particularly given the urgent need to protect the population's right to life and health without immediately resorting to the most intrusive measures.

At the beginning of the pandemic, the right to life and health understandably dominated, with other rights gaining more weight as the situation evolved. Paula O. does not identify deliberate or systematic misuse of human rights justifications but notes that different rights were sometimes interpreted inconsistently depending on context. For example, freedom of enterprise and the right to work were weighed differently across sectors, such as comparing restrictions on restaurants with bans on cultural events, producing uneven impacts on livelihoods.

Nevertheless, she emphasizes that public debate remained possible, and policy outcomes appeared to reflect negotiated compromises rather than unilateral imposition. At the beginning of the pandemic, the right to life and health understandably dominated, with other rights gaining more weight as the situation evolved. Susan H. and Sara L. took a very similar stance, neither considering that the state actors would have interfered unnecessarily with the rights of the child or human rights or downplayed other rights in order to introduce restrictive measures.

Sara L.'s organization, an established human rights NGO, was not that focused on COVID-19 issues per se but was mainly working on their pre-planned human rights initiatives. In this regard, Sarah L. provides an interesting self-critical reflection by acknowledging that neither her organization nor the broader human rights NGO community identified or articulated major rights violations linked to COVID-19 measures at the time. They rather relied on guidance from national authorities and the Finnish Institute for Health and Welfare (THL). In practice, she sees this having resulted in a cautious, administration-oriented approach, including advising individuals to seek redress through official channels rather than mobilizing overt public critique. Paula O. shared these self-critical views while noting that, at the time, the research produced by the relevant Finnish institutions was reliable and of high quality. She further pointed out that, in the context of 2026 characterized by substantial budget cuts affecting governance and administrative bodies, as well as the overarching securitization discourse that tends to override human rights concerns, the approach adopted by human rights NGOs during the COVID-19 pandemic might need to be reconsidered should a new pandemic arise.

Generally, both Paula O. and Sara L. consider that the Finnish government demonstrated a genuine will to take fundamental and human rights into account decision-making regarding the restrictive measures. Though she identifies considerable variation in the quality and depth of fundamental and human rights impact assessments and shortcomings existed, the practices

evolved in a more positive direction as the pandemic progressed. In comparative perspective, Paula O. views Finland's response as relatively balanced and, in some respects, more rights-respecting than that of several other European states. She contrasts Finland with countries such as Sweden, where minimal restrictions led to significant suffering among older populations, even if overall mortality differences were less dramatic. In her assessment, crises redistribute burdens unevenly. In Finland, children and young people bore a disproportionate share of the costs of restrictions, whereas in Sweden the elderly were more severely affected.

As mentioned above, Sara L., Paula O. and Susan H. all mentioned closing of educational institutions and shifting to remote education having been an example of a restrictive measure they in retrospective perceive as too far-reaching.

As a central concern and point of critique, Paula O. pointed out that when introducing COVID-19-restrictive measures, lawmakers focused predominantly on the national fundamental rights framework, while international human rights obligations were addressed only superficially. References to international treaties were often cursory and lacked substantive analysis of their concrete legal requirements. This, she argues, revealed a conceptual inconsistency since even though Finland's domestic fundamental rights system operated under emergency conditions, which allows for certain provisional limitations, the international human rights system less accepting of such limitations, did not. Yet this distinction was rarely reflected in practical impact assessments. Paula O. suggests that such imbalance may stem from the international human rights system being less well known among lawmakers or from the somewhat faulty assumption that international obligations are fully absorbed into the domestic constitutional framework. Regardless of its cause, such an imbalance risks lowering the level of human rights protection during emergencies.

According to Paula O., Finland should have submitted a formal derogation notification under relevant international human rights treaties, including the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights and the European Convention on Human Rights. Such a notification would have clarified the exceptional nature of the measures and helped prevent the normalization of the exceptional human rights restrictions during and after the crisis. In her view, Finland's failure to issue such a notification represented a structural weakness in its human rights approach, a structural weakness in Finland's human rights governance during the pandemic.

Paula O. further points to ambiguities in questions over competence, noting that it was not always clear which decisions fell within the remit of political decision-makers, and which were the responsibility of civil servants. In addition, public communication did not consistently distinguish between legally binding rules and non-binding recommendations, leaving many citizens uncertain about their obligations.

Sweden

In contrast to Finland, Sweden's constitutional framework does not permit the declaration of a state of emergency in peacetime crises. As a result, the country operated largely within its ordinary regulatory framework and introduced minimal new legislation specifically addressing the COVID-19-pandemic. While this avoided formal emergency derogations, it also meant that there were fewer law drafting processes generating documentation that could be examined for the quality of human and fundamental rights impact assessments. Both Swedish interviewees,

Johanna A. and Lena K. regard discussions of human rights implications as largely insufficient under these conditions.

Lena K. emphasizes that the absence of formal legislative processes and preparatory works made it difficult to assess whether right-based considerations were systematically weighed. She identifies a notable lack of child rights analysis, particularly concerning vulnerable groups such as children with disabilities. Decisions tended to rely on a one-size-fits-all logic, neglecting the differentiated needs of children in diverse circumstances. Generally, in terms of safeguards for children's rights in Sweden, she expressed concern that there are minimal protections against rights violations especially those available for individuals, but these issues seem to be rather dependent on the goodwill of decision-makers. At the same time the current system suffers from the lack of robust monitoring mechanism for children's rights, which hampers effective oversight. Despite these significant shortcomings, Lena K did not identify deliberate misuse of human rights justifications in reasoning actions or inactions concerning COVID-19-pandemic. Neither she considered Sweden's decisions having been overly broad.

Johanna A.'s assessment is far more critical. She concludes that the balancing of rights during the pandemic failed fundamentally in Sweden. Although authorities claimed to act in children's best interests, they denied children meaningful access to health protections. In her view, Sweden's minimalist and neoliberal approach prioritized economic continuity and societal "normalcy" over children's rights to health and life, resulting in arbitrary and unequal outcomes. She is particularly critical of the government's refusal to introduce protective measures for children, arguing that this failure directly undermined children's physical and mental well-being.

3.5 Impacts on equality

Across all interviews, there was a broad consensus that the COVID-19 responses implemented in Finland and Sweden did not affect children equally. All the interviewees emphasized that socio-economically disadvantaged children and children at risk of domestic abuse were disproportionately harmed by pandemic-related restrictions. In both countries, measures such as school closures, the suspension of leisure activities, and restrictions on social interaction deepened pre-existing structural inequalities, leaving already vulnerable children with fewer protective mechanisms and supportive structures. To further illustrate that point, several interviewees brought up the disruption of child protection and welfare services during lockdown periods. Susan H. described how social services in Finland struggled to reach at-risk children when schools and extracurricular activities were closed. The absence of leisure activities and the reduced presence of trusted adults in public spaces further diminished opportunities for early intervention. Consequently, many children, particularly those vulnerable, were left to navigate their challenges largely on their own. While some leisure activities, such as sports clubs, remained open in Sweden, cultural activities were often restricted, limiting children's opportunities for socialization and self-expression.

Finland moved to remote education on two occasions during the pandemic. While interviewees generally did not contest these decisions from a human rights perspective at the time, in hindsight they acknowledged that the shift to distance learning had disproportionate effects, especially on children in vulnerable situations. Children from socio-economically

disadvantaged households often lacked adequate digital equipment, quiet study environments, or adult support for learning. The Finnish interviewees noted that municipalities varied considerably in their capacity to support disadvantaged pupils, contributing to unequal outcomes. Where schools were closed and municipalities had troubles organizing alternative meal provision in an accessible manner, some children's nutritional needs were at times compromised.

Children with migrant backgrounds were identified as facing particular challenges in both Finland and Sweden. In Finland, children whose first language was neither Finnish nor Swedish were disproportionately affected by the lack of in-person teaching and individualized support. Language barriers complicated participation in remote education and limited families' understanding of rapidly changing rules and recommendations. Interviewees also noted shortcomings in multilingual information dissemination, which made it difficult for some families to access essential information regarding schooling, health measures, and available support services.

Susan H. and Paula O. raised concerns that immigrant children in Finland with residence permits tied to their guardians' employment might have faced increased stress, possibly compounding the psychological impact of pandemic-related job losses or income insecurity. The pandemic also disrupted asylum and family reunification procedures, with delays, suspended identification processes at embassies, and border closures limiting access to protection mechanisms. Taken together, these factors illustrate how pandemic-related measures intersected with pre-existing vulnerabilities, producing unequal and, in many cases, long-lasting effects on children's rights, well-being, and opportunities.

Regarding equality and non-discrimination impact assessments in the context of Sweden, Lena K. suggested that systematic human rights, equality, and child impact assessments were generally not conducted prior to the introduction of COVID-19 restrictions. Although some retrospective evaluations were later carried out, these mainly occurred only after measures had already been implemented. The absence of pre-emptive assessments meant that the foreseeable impacts of restrictions on vulnerable groups were insufficiently considered. Lena K. partly attributed this failure to the lack of comprehensive and binding national guidelines for conducting child rights impact assessments in governmental decision-making. According to Johanna A. equality and non-discrimination assessments may have been formally attempted, she regarded them as ineffective in practice. Furthermore, she recalled how public discourse in Sweden at times explicitly blamed immigrants for virus transmission, reinforcing stigmatization and discrimination instead of calling for accountability in decision-making.

Susan H., Sara L., and Paula O. did not recall that comprehensive equality impact assessments were conducted prior to the introduction of specific restrictive measures. They attributed this absence primarily to the urgency of the situation, as well as to limited knowledge and lack of experiential evidence regarding how such measures might affect children in different contexts. Susan H. further described how, later in the pandemic, more systematic data on these impacts began to emerge, contributing to increasingly critical public discourse surrounding restrictive measures affecting children. This critical stance was informed by growing recognition that the measures did not affect children equally.

4. Conclusion

4.1 COVID-19: Lessons learned?

When asked to assess which safeguards should be strengthened to ensure better protection of children's rights in future emergencies similar to the COVID-19 pandemic, the interviewees raised largely convergent points. A Finnish interviewee, Sara L. emphasized that future crisis preparedness requires strengthening both institutional frameworks and the resilience of civil society organizations. She highlighted key national actors, such as the Ombudsman for Children, the Non-Discrimination Ombudsman, and the Human Rights Centre, as institutions whose roles could be further consolidated and clarified in emergency governance. Lena K. proposed similar structural changes as a means of strengthening safeguards in Sweden.

According to Sara L., greater coordination, cooperation, and sustained dialogue among human rights actors are also needed, alongside the systematic integration of human and children's rights perspectives into emergency response structures. She further suggested that civil society participation could be enhanced through clearer coordination mechanisms, including the designation of a lead organization empowered to represent a broader range of civil society actors in crisis-related decision-making. All Finnish interviewees, however, noted that the resilience of Finnish civil society is currently undermined by significant funding cuts affecting non-governmental organizations in the coming years. Susan H., for example, observed that while her organization played a substantial role in producing and disseminating knowledge about the impacts of the pandemic, its current resources might be insufficient to sustain such efforts should another pandemic occur.

As new legislation was introduced in Finland, the Constitutional Law Committee of Parliament played a significant role in the *ex ante* review of COVID-19-related legislative measures and governmental decrees adopted under the Emergency Powers Act, assessing their compatibility with the Constitution and with international human rights treaties. According to Paula O., this review partially addressed perspectives that human rights NGOs might have raised had they had the opportunity and resources to engage more actively in decision-making. In crises such as the pandemic, the importance of *ex ante* constitutional and human rights review becomes particularly evident, highlighting the need for reliable and impartial oversight. This issue has become the subject of considerable academic and public debate in Finland as the Constitutional Law Committee is increasingly perceived as politicized.

Finally, all interviewees underscored the need for substantive, non-mechanistic fundamental and human rights impact assessments, as well as equality and child impact assessments, that genuinely inform decision-making rather than functioning merely as procedural formalities.

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4.1 Concluding remarks

Only one interviewee was willing to quite comprehensively challenge their government's COVID-19 response. However, many interviewees expressed that adjustments should have been made to better accommodate children, particularly vulnerable groups of children, and to improve methods of child and human rights impact assessments. Most interviewees did not perceive a disregard for civil society views among decision-makers at the local, regional, or municipal levels, instead attributing the lack of interaction to the immense pressure and urgency surrounding the implementation of COVID-19 countermeasures.

Notably, the relative lack of civil society engagement was not the primary concern for interviewees working in the fields of children's rights and human rights. Many acknowledged that they might not have been able to contribute effectively even if given the opportunity, citing limited resources, insufficient expertise and their organizations' reliance on information produced by national authorities and health institutions. Across the interviews, a shared concern emerged regarding the adequacy of existing legal and institutional frameworks for safeguarding children's rights and human rights in future crisis situations.

Interviewees in both Finland and Sweden suggested the development of an emergency response strategy that formally integrates human rights bodies such as the Non-Discrimination Ombudsman and the Ombudsman for Children into decision-making processes. They believed that such a structure could function flexibly, drawing on all available information to better ensure the protection of fundamental and human rights during crises. Thus, rather than advocating broad public debate over emergency measures during states of emergency, interviewees called for the systematic integration of human and children's rights perspectives into administrative decision-making. They emphasized that relevant human rights bodies should not merely be consulted but involved from the outset.

Experts in their field in both Finland and Sweden also stressed the role of supranational and international regimes. Johanna A., drawing on her experience of the Swedish COVID-19 response, underscored the importance of strengthened coordination at the European level. In her view, closer EU-level cooperation could establish clearer and more consistent standards, limit national exceptionalism, and contribute to more uniform protection of children's rights in future health emergencies. Finnish interviewees, in turn, expressed concern that derogations from international human rights treaties risk becoming normalized through persistent crisis-oriented discourse.

Based on these interviews, there was no widespread fear that states were prone to misusing human rights justifications or rights-based language to legitimize governance decisions at the expense of individual rights. Nevertheless, every interviewee identified structural design flaws that could, particularly in times of crisis, place states in situations where human rights protection is significantly weakened. Across the interviews, a clear need emerged for stronger safeguards for human rights and children's rights, as well as more robust systems of checks and balances.

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